

and accurate synchronization of the nodes. When two synchronized nodes are far apart, the calibration becomes a relatively complicated matter. Calibration consists of local asymmetry calibration and fibre delay asymmetry. Principles of White Rabbit calibration are discussed in [3] and practically evaluated in [4]. Method for the automatic evaluation of asymmetry in the optical transmission path is shown in [5].

IV. LONG HAUL FRIENDLY SOLUTION

Chapter II indicated also possibility of regenerated and retimed solution, it has been tested e.g. here [6] and also deployed here [7]. However this solution requires to perform calibration of each segment and its recalibration in case of any service works having significant influence on fibre length or other source of asymmetry. This can be avoided by deployment optically amplified solution. Such solution has been shown by [8] or [9].

To compare two previously mentioned scenarios we set in laboratory setup consisting of 4 times 100 km of G.652D fibre on spools, each spool 50km. Laboratory setup consists of two WR switch devices, configured as grand master and slave, as shown in Fig. 1. The WR system utilizes commercial Small Form Pluggable (SFP) transceivers. Therefore, we have used the pair of 1.25 Gbps SFPs designed for channels 8 and 9 of Dense Wavelength Division Multiplex (DWDM) (wavelengths 1571.24 and 1570.42 nm) featuring extended input sensitivity of -32 dBm and +1 dBm or higher output power. At first, the attenuation of the whole line was compensated by three fully bidirectional EDFA amplifiers CzechLight with single path for signal in both directions placed in between spans. Determined Maximal time interval error (MTIE) is shown in Fig 2 with orange line. Later we replace these amplifiers with WRSes. Measured MTIE is shown in Fig 2. by blue line.

To achieve reliable operations, we will consider dual power supply solutions both for WRs and also for bidirectional EDFA amplifiers with remote management. Setting cost of such amplifier to about 0.2 of cost fully featured WRs we are getting cost comparison of regenerated (blue) and amplified solution (orange). Number of inline huts is on X axis.

CONCLUSION

We continue with verification of appropriate setups of long haul WR lines with excessive attenuations (over optical budget of SFP transceivers). On laboratory 400 km fibre setup we measured that both regenerated and amplifies scenarios will keep target sub ns MTIE. However amplified setup overperforms regenerated setup in terms of MTIE and CAPEX and OPEX costs. As our measurement still continuous we are planning to verify behaviour over real fibres buried in ground.

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Fig. 2. MTIE[s] for regenerated solution in Blue and amplified solution in Orange.

Fig. 3. Arbitrary cost comparison regenerated in Blue and amplified solution in Orange. Number of inline huts on X axis.

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